

MEDICAL SCIENCES

DYSLIPIDEMIA AND POLYMORPHISM OF FGB FIBRINOGEN GENE IN PATIENTS WITH ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION

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Abstract

Objective - is to assess lipid levels and identify polymorphism of the FGB fibrinogen gene in patients with arterial hypertension (AH).

Materials and methods. The study included 76 patients with AH (main group) and 24 patients without this pathology (control group). The main group was divided into 3 clinical groups: the 1st group included 29 patients with hypertension, the 2nd group - 23 patients with hypertension and coronary heart disease, the 3rd group - 24 patients with a combination of AH with CAD and type 2 DM. The number of platelets in the blood, body mass index (BMI), blood pressure (SBP/DBP) was measured. The concentrations of total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) were determined in the blood using test kits. The level of very low lipoprotein cholesterol (VLDL-C) and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) and the atherogenic index (AI) were calculated using the formulas. Determination of the polymorphism of the fibrinogen gene FGB in the blood was carried out by mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF) on a Seguenon mass spectrometer (USA). Statistical analysis included mean, standard deviation, Fisher's test (F), χ^2 method with Yates correction, odds ratio (OR-odds ratio) with 95% confidence interval.

Results. Hypercholesterolemia in the 1st group was detected in 48.3% of cases, in the 2nd and 3rd groups - 43.5% and 37.5%, respectively. Hypertriglyceridemia in 1st, 2nd and 3rd groups was observed in 51.7%, 39.1% and 50.0%, respectively. The prevalence of the G/G genotype among patients with AH was 69.0%, among patients with AH and CAD - 87.0%, and in patients with AH and CAD and DM - 58.3%. The heterozygous genotype G/A among patients of the 3rd group was found in 33.3%, the 1st group - in 24.1% and the 2nd group - in 4.3%. The A/A genotype were detected in the 1st, 2nd and 3rd groups in 6.9%, 8.7% and 8.3% of cases, respectively.

Conclusion. The dominant type of dyslipidemia was hypertriglyceridemia. Heterozygous G/A genotype was more common in patients with AH, CAD and DM compared to patients with AH and CAD ($p < 0.05$). The chance of meeting patients with heterozygous G/A genotype among patients with AH is 7 times higher ($p < 0.05$). Well-designed large-scale studies in larger populations are needed to confirm this finding.

Keywords: arterial hypertension, dyslipidemia, fibrinogen gene FGB, polymorphism, genotype, odds ratio.

The lipid profile is one of a group of tests that are often performed together to identify the risk of cardiovascular disease (CVD). These tests are used as potential indicators of the likelihood of a heart attack or stroke caused by a blockage in blood vessels or hardening of the arteries. Elevated levels of total cholesterol (TCH), triglycerides (TG), and low-density lipoproteins (LDL) have been found to be associated with an increased risk of coronary heart disease (CHD) and ischemic stroke [1]. It has been reported about the importance of assessing the lipid profile and their ratio even in a healthy person, since they are atherogenic factors in the development of myocardial infarction and other coronary complications [2].

Dyslipidemia, being one of the main causes of coronary artery disease, is characterized by an increase in the serum level of total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) or TG and a decrease in the concentration of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) in the blood serum [1-4]. They are usually evaluated for the purpose of determining cardiovascular risk. The prevalence of dyslipidemia varies geographically; although it is estimated that more than 50% of the adult population suffers from dyslipidemia worldwide [1-4]. The results of a multicenter cohort study conducted in Azerbaijan showed that abdominal obesity is one of the most pronounced risk factors among both men and women with AH, and the average

values of TCH in the blood of patients with AH met the criteria for mild hypercholesterolemia [5].

However, although the association of high TG levels with CVD, especially atherosclerotic CVD, has been well documented in large cohort studies [6], the role of TG as an independent CV risk factor remains controversial [7]. Although it has been suggested that HDL-C is protective against CVD, due in part to its role in reverse cholesterol transport [8], some studies have reported that high or normal levels of HDL-C do not protect against CVD [9]. A single level of HDL-C in the blood serum reflects the HDL-C pool, and not its functionality [9].

Studies have shown that plasma fibrinogen concentration is an independent risk factor for cardiovascular and thrombotic diseases [10, 11]. It is believed that the FGB (Fibrinogen Beta Chain) gene clearly affects the level of fibrinogen in plasma, which has been confirmed by studies [10, 11]. Several meta-analyses have shown that 2 FGB gene polymorphisms are associated with an increased risk of CAD [12, 13].

The aim of this study was to assess lipid levels and identify polymorphisms of the FGB fibrinogen gene in patients with arterial hypertension.

Materials and methods of research. Examinations of patients are in accordance with the protocol of the ethics committee. The study included 76 patients with hypertension and 24 patients without this pathology (control group). The inclusion criteria for the

study were: - age from 32 to 77 years; - patients of both sexes; - typical pain syndrome; - the appearance of a new Q wave on the electrocardiogram (ECG); - dynamics of the ST-segment and T wave on the ECG; - dynamics of markers of myocardial damage. Criteria for exclusion from the study: - patients with angina pectoris; - patients who have had a myocardial infarction or with acute myocardial infarction; - age under 30 and over 77; - pregnancy; - patients with excess weight, obesity; - severe hypertension; - acute disorders of cerebral circulation; - acute myocardial infarction, acute coronary syndrome, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; - mental disorders. The patients who took part in the study were informed about the purpose of the study and gave their written consent to participate. The study was guided by the ethical principles of the Helsinki Declaration.

The main and control groups included patients aged 32 to 77 years and 26 to 61 years, respectively. Depending on the presence of IHD and diabetes mellitus (DM), the main group was divided into 3 clinical groups: the 1st group included 29 patients with AH, the 2nd group - 23 patients with AH and CAD, the 3rd group - 24 patients with a combination of AH with CAD and DM type 2. The control group consisted of individuals without these diseases.

When examining patients, we were guided by the practical recommendations of the International Society of Hypertension 2020 [14]. All patients underwent a complete blood count, special attention was paid to the number of platelets, body mass index (BMI), blood pressure (SBP / DBP) were also measured. BMI was determined by the formula: $BMI = \frac{weight (kg)}{height (m^2)}$. The concentration of total cholesterol and triglycerides was determined using the test Cholesterol liquicolor) CHOD -

PAP method and Triglycerides liquicolormono GPO-PAP method of Human (Germany), respectively. The level of HDL-C was determined by the enzymatic colorimetric method using the Roche Diagnostics test system (Switzerland) according to the attached instructions. The level of very low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (VLDL-C) and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) was calculated using the formulas:

$$VLDL-C = TG / 2.2$$

$$LDL-C = \text{total cholesterol} - (HDL-C + TG / 5).$$

In order to assess changes in lipid metabolism and the state of the vascular endothelium, the atherogenic index (AI) was calculated using the formula: $\frac{TCH-HDL}{HDL}$

Determination of the polymorphism of the fibrinogen gene FGB was carried out by mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF) on a Seguenon mass spectrometer (USA). The study material was whole blood.

Statistical processing of the results and construction of tables and graphs was carried out using the Microsoft Office Excel, Statistical 16.0 application package on a computer according to the proposed standard methods of variation statistics. Mean value, mean deviation, Fisher's test (F) were calculated. The frequency of occurrence of individual genotypes was determined as the percentage of individuals carrying the genotype to the total number of those examined. To find differences between qualitative indicators, the χ^2 method was used with Yates' correction for continuity. The odds ratio (OR-odds ratio) was calculated with a 95% confidence interval. All analyzes were performed at a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Results. The analysis showed no significant age and gender differences between the study groups (Table 1).

Table 1.

Demographic and clinical parameters in patients of study groups

Indicator	the 1 st group (n=29)	the 2 nd group (n=23)	the 3 rd group (n=24)	Control group (n=24)	p
Average age, years	50,62±8,55	58,30±7,59	59,21±4,62	45,87±8,35	>0,05
Men, n (%)	19 (65,5)	17 (73,9)	15 (62,5)	15 (62,5)	>0,05
Women, n (%)	10 (34,5)	6 (26,1)	9 (37,5)	9 (37,5)	>0,05
BMI, kg/m ²	30,49±3,72	29,66±3,80	31,44±3,33	28,08±2,76	>0,05
SBP, mm Hg	148,97±14,86	139,78±15,48	144,88±18,45	119,58±6,42	>0,05
DBP, mm Hg	93,08±11,06	85,65±11,98	85,46±13,0	76,75±5,21	>0,05
Platelets, 10 ⁹ /l	188,95±35,53	205,09±45,41	213,42±39,22	201,71±29,66	>0,05

Note: p - statistical significance of differences in indicators with the control group

From Table 1 it follows that in clinical groups, BMI was statistically slightly higher than the control value. Systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) in comparison with the control group in the 1st, 2nd and 3rd groups was higher by 19.7 and 17.5%, 14.4 and 10.4%, 17.5 and 10.2 % respectively. The average number of platelets in patients of the 1st group was slightly lower (by 6.3%) than in the

control group. On the contrary, in patients of the 2nd and 3rd groups, the number of platelets, on average, statistically insignificantly exceeded the control indicator by 1.7% and 5.5%, respectively.

The levels of TG, VLDL cholesterol in blood serum were higher in patients of all three clinical groups (Table 2).

Table 2.

The level of components of the lipid profile in patients of the study groups

Indicator	the 1 st group (n=29)	the 2 nd group (n=23)	the 3 rd group (n=24)	Control group (n=24)	p
Total cholesterol, mg/dl	196,76±38,92	180,26±49,08	185,58±57,81	183,21±28,14	>0,05
TG, mg/dl	191,93±90,31	178,04±104,49	204,5±106,25	164,96±101,27	>0,05
VLDL-C, mg/dl	36,49±15,29	35,55±21,0	41,32±21,02	32,92±20,13	>0,05
LDL-C, mg/dl	108,30±31,11	98,15±32,84	97,0±47,92	101,71±20,16	>0,05
HDL-C, mg/dl	43,48±10,53	42,48±7,89	41,37±8,54	43,17±10,97	>0,05
Atherogenic index	3,87±1,34	3,51±1,49	3,69±1,23	3,68±1,44	>0,05

Note: p - statistical significance of differences in indicators with the control group.

From the data in Table 2 it can be seen that relatively high levels of total cholesterol and LDL-C were detected in patients of 1st group. Hypercholesterolemia in 1st group (reference value >190 mg/dl) was detected in 48.3% of cases, in 2nd and 3rd groups - 43.5% and 37.5%, respectively. In the control group, such cases amounted to 37.5%. Hypertriglyceridemia (>150 mg / dl) in the 1st, 2nd and 3rd groups was noted in 51.7%, 39.1% and 50.0%, respectively. Hypertriglyceridemia in patients of the control group was 37.5%. The concentration of VLDL-C above 40 mg / dl in patients in the 1st, 2nd and 3rd groups was detected in 26.7%, 30.4% and 33.3%, respectively, and in the control group - in 29.2% of cases. A high level (>115 mg / dl) of LDL-C in the 1st, 2nd and 3rd groups was noted in 41.4%, 34.8% and 33.3% of cases, respectively. In the control group, high levels of LDL-C occurred in 25.0% of cases. Patients with HDL-C concentration below 40 mg / dl, which is considered a reference value, in the 1st, 2nd and 3rd groups amounted to 48.3%, 43.5% and 50.0%, respectively, in the control group - 54.2%. A high level of atherogenic index (>3.5) in the 1st, 2nd and 3rd groups was observed in 55.2%, 34.8% and 45.8% of cases, respectively. In the control group, IA exceeding 3.5 was

detected in 25.0% of cases. The number of platelets in the blood, exceeding the reference values (150-380x10⁹/l), was detected only in 1 (4.3%) patient of the 2nd group, and the number of platelets below the reference value (<150x10⁹/l) was detected in 6 (20.7%), 3 (13.0%) and 3 (12.5%) patients in the 1st, 2nd and 3rd groups, respectively, as well as in 1 (4.2%) patient of the control group.

An analysis of the polymorphism of the FGB fibrinogen gene indicated the prevalence of the G/G genotype in all study groups (Fig. 1).

As follows from Fig. 1, the distribution of G/G genotypes of FGB fibrinogen polymorphism did not show significant differences between the 2nd and 3rd groups of patients and the control group (p>0.05). In the 2nd group, there was a statistically significant difference in G/G genotypes with the control group ($\chi^2=3.485$, F=0.049, p<0.05). Between the 1st and 2nd groups ($\chi^2=1.435$, F=0.188, p>0.05), as well as the 1st and 3rd groups ($\chi^2=0.266$, F=0.566, p>0.05) there is a significant difference in the frequency of the G/G genotype was not revealed. The distribution of G/G genotypes between the 2nd and 3rd groups of patients had statistical significance - $\chi^2=3.485$, F=0.049 (p<0.05).

Fig.1. The frequency of genotypes of the fibrinogen gene FGB in the examined patients (%)

The distribution of the G/A genotype did not show significant differences in patients of the 1st and 3rd groups with the control group (p>0.05). The distribution of the frequency of the G/A genotype in patients of

the 2nd group and the control group had a statistical significance of differences ($\chi^2=7.161$, F=0.004, p<0.05). Comparative analysis of the frequency of the G/A genotype between clinical groups showed that between the 1st and 2nd groups ($\chi^2=2.489$, F=0.063, p>0.05), as well

as the 1st and 3rd groups ($\chi^2=0.188$, $F=0.547$, $p > 0.05$) there were no significant differences. The frequency distribution of the G/A genotype in patients of the 2nd and 3rd groups had a statistically significant difference ($\chi^2=4.639$, $F=0.023$, $p < 0.05$).

The frequency of the A/A genotype was relatively high in patients of the 2nd group and was not detected in the control group (Fig. 1). The statistical evaluation of the distribution of the A/A genotype did not show significant differences between the groups of patients ($p > 0.05$).

Statistical analysis of the odds ratio (OR) between the 1st and 2nd groups showed that the chance of meeting patients with homozygous G/G genotype in the 1st group (with AH) was 2.222, in the 2nd group (AH with CAD) - 6.667 (OR-0.333, 95 % CI 0.078-1.416, $p > 0.05$). The chance of meeting patients with heterozygous G/A genotype in patients in the 1st group was

0.318, in the 2nd group - 0.045 (OR-7.0, 95% CI 0.794-61.743, $p < 0.05$). The chance of meeting a patient with a homozygous A/A mutant genotype among patients of the 1st group (with hypertension) was 0.074, among patients of 2nd group (with hypertension and coronary artery disease) - 0.095 (OR-0.778, 95% CI 0.101-5.989, $p > 0.05$). Statistical analysis of the odds ratio between the 1st and 3rd groups showed that the chance of meeting a patient with the G/G genotype in the 3rd group was 1.400 (OR-1.587, 95% CI 0.513-4.915, $p > 0.05$), with the G/A genotype and A/A was 0.500 (OR-0.636, 95% CI 0.191-2.116, $p > 0.05$) and 0.091 (OR-0.815, 95% CI 0.106-6.262, $p > 0.05$).

In the course of the study, the average levels of platelets and lipid parameters were analyzed in patients with different variants of the FGB gene genotypes in patients of the study groups.

Table 3.

Mean values of platelets and lipid parameters in patients with FGB gene polymorphism

Indicator	Genotype														
	G/G						G/A						A/A		
	the 1st gr.	the 2nd gr.	the 3rd gr.	Counter. gr.	the 1st gr.	II rp	the 2nd gr.	Counter. gr.	the 1st gr.	the 2nd gr.	the 3rd gr.	Counter. gr.			
Platelets, 109/l	198,03 ±40,93	200,55 ±42,7	203,36 ±36,16	202,28 ±30,22	172,57 ±31,92	-	221,12 ±46,62	200,9 ±29,1	160,5 ±3,5	270,5 ±62,5	253,0 ±34,0	-			
TCH, mg/dl	206,35 ±40,25	176,55 ±51,06	174,0 ±42,28	184,86 ±29,43	181,0 ±28,28	-	202,87 ±65,41	180,9 ±25,88	156,0 ±26,0	196,0 ±25,0	197,5 ±86,5	-			
TG, mg/dl	205,65 ±112,91	171,4 ±96,18	246,86 ±135,57	165,57 ±99,90	150,57 ±43,63	-	159,0 ±30,25	164,1 ±103,52	199,5 ±27,5	98,0 ±7,0	90,0 ±21,0	-			
VLDL-C, mg/dl	38,47 ±18,64	34,21 ±19,41	50,16 ±26,41	33,01 ±1,85	29,86 ±9,08	-	31,67 ±5,94	32,78 ±20,58	39,9 ±5,5	19,6 ±1,4	18,0 ±4,0	-			
LDL-C, mg/dl	115,14 ±33,56	94,97 ±33,82	82,36 ±37,89	100,86 ±22,43	99,0 ±17,71	-	117,37 ±48,53	102,9 ±17,26	72,5 ±21,5	130,5 ±27,5	118,0 ±58,0	-			
HDL-C, mg/dl	43,40 ±12,38	42,7 ±8,27	39,57 ±6,79	47,86 ±13,12	43,86 ±5,31	-	43,37 ±10,53	36,6 ±5,68	43,0 ±10,0	45,5 ±1,5	46,0 ±9,0	-			
Atherogenic index	4,20 ±1,36	3,30 ±1,33	3,55 ±1,33	3,23 ±1,25	3,25 ±0,98	-	3,58 ±0,61	4,28 ±1,60	2,68 ±0,25	3,33 ±0,69	3,08 ±1,08	-			

As can be seen from Table 3, in the 1st group, on average, the largest number of platelets, an increased concentration of total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL-C and the value of the atherogenic index were observed in patients with the homozygous G/G genotype. In this group, a relatively high VLDL-C and a low HDL-C were observed in patients with the A/A genotype. In group II, the G/A genotype was detected in 1 patient, and therefore, the average values of the studied parameters in patients with the G/G and A/A genotypes were calculated. In this group, an increased number of platelets, elevated levels of total cholesterol, LDL-C, AI and reduced HDL-C were detected in patients with the A/A genotype, high concentrations of TG, VLDL-C were observed in patients with the G/G genotype. In the III clinical group, an increased platelet count, LDL-C in patients were determined with the A/A genotype, an increased TG value, VLDL-C and a reduced level of HDL-C were observed in patients with the G/G genotype, and an increased content of total cholesterol and an IA indicator were detected in patients with heterozygous G/A genotype.

Consequently, an increased number of platelets, LDL-C among the examined patients of all three groups were more often detected in carriers of the AA genotype, an increased level of TG, VLDL-C, and a reduced level of HDL-C - in carriers of the G/G genotype.

Discussion. Hypertension and dyslipidaemia often coexist; both contribute to CVD, and are two major independent risk factors for CVD. Dyslipidemia plays a role in endothelial dysfunction, which in turn plays a central role in the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis, thrombosis, insulin resistance and hypertension. Our results clearly showed that dyslipidemia occurred in patients of all clinical groups. It has been shown that TG-rich lipoproteins and LDL-C are toxic to endothelial cells, but HDL-C has a protective effect [15]. A high atherogenic index, which is known to reflect a violation of cholesterol metabolism, was detected in 55.2% of patients with AH, in 45.8% of patients with AH, CAD and type 2 DM, and in 34.8% of patients with AH and CAD. The frequency of an increased atherogenic index among patients with hypertension may have indicated a high risk of developing CAD in these patients. High serum cholesterol levels are known to increase the risk of macrovascular complications such as CAD [16]. In the healthy population, baseline levels of LDL-C and HDL-C have been reported to be significantly associated with the risk of ischemic stroke [15]. It should be noted that often the complexity of patients with hypertension is not taken into account, often focusing on the assessment of one main risk factor for CVD and ignoring the fact that excessive obesity plays a key role in impaired glucose and lipid metabolism, which leads to a more atherogenic lipid profile. We believe that the control of both hypertension and hypercholesterolemia should be a universal and mandatory goal of CVD prevention.

According to our results, hypertriglyceridemia was diagnosed in 51.7% of patients with AH, in 39.1% of patients with AH and CAD, and in 50.0% of patients with AH, CAD and DM. Although the role of hypertriglyceridemia may not receive as much attention as the

role of plasma cholesterol in CVD, plasma TG, especially non-fasting TG, is believed to be correlated with the risk of ischemic stroke. It is believed that hypertriglyceridemia may increase the risk of ischemic stroke by promoting atherosclerosis and thrombosis and increasing blood viscosity [17]. The literature reports a positive relationship between total cholesterol, LDL-C and TG with ischemic stroke [18]. However, further studies are needed to elucidate the role of hypertriglyceridemia in the development and prognosis of ischemic stroke.

Platelet aggregation plays a central role in the pathogenesis of acute thrombosis in IHD and stroke. FGB polymorphisms may be involved in the etiology of ischemic stroke. The FGB gene provides instructions for making a protein called the fibrinogen B beta (B β) chain, one part (subunit) of the fibrinogen protein. Based on epidemiological and biochemical studies, it was established that the FGB 455 G/A polymorphism is one of the strongest genetic variations [12, 18]. We examined the frequency of three genetic variants of the FGB gene. The obtained results showed the frequent occurrence of the homozygous genotype G/G of the FGB gene in patients with AH, AH+CAD and AH+ CAD +DM, as well as in the control group. The study revealed that the prevalence of the G/G genotype among the examined patients with AH was 69.0%, among patients with AH and CAD - 87.0%, and in patients with AH and CAD and DM - 58.3%. At the same time, the heterozygous G/A genotype was most common among patients with AH on the background of CAD and DM - 33.3%, and among patients with AH it was found in 24.1% and among patients with AH and CAD - in 4.3%. In the control group, we identified only the homozygous G/G genotype (58.3%) and the heterozygous G/A genotype (41.7%), and the frequency of occurrence of the G/G genotype did not differ from the frequency in the group of patients with AH, CAD, and DM. Our results partially agree with the data of G. Durmus et al. [19], who observed only G/G, G/A genotypes in the FGB gene, and their frequency was 66.7% and 33.3% in the group of patients with coronary artery disease, and 83.3% and 16.7% in the control group, respectively. The authors did not observe the A/A genotype in any of the groups [19]. In our study, the homozygous A/A mutant genotype was detected in all clinical groups, amounting to 6.9%, 8.7%, and 8.3%, respectively, among patients with AH, AH, and CAD, AH, CAD, and DM. It should be noted that the exact mechanism by which the FGB G/A polymorphism may influence the pathology of ischemic stroke remains unknown.

Based on the results of the study of the association of platelet levels and lipid metabolism with FGB gene genotypes, an increased number of platelets, a high level of LDL-C among the examined patients in carriers of the homozygous mutant AA genotype, an increased level of triglycerides, VLDL-C, a reduced level of HDL-C in carriers of the homozygous G/G genotype.

Conclusion. The present study demonstrated a relatively high prevalence of dyslipidemia among the patients with AH, moreover, there were various forms

of dyslipidemia, but hypertriglyceridemia was the dominant type of dyslipidemia. The distribution of the homozygous G/G genotype and the homozygous mutant genotype A/A of the FGB gene showed no significant differences between the patient groups and the control group ($p > 0.05$). The heterozygous G/A genotype was more common in patients with AH, CAD, and DM than in patients with AH and CAD ($p < 0.05$). The chance to meet patients with heterozygous G/A genotype among patients with AH is 7 times higher ($p < 0.05$) than among patients with AH and CAD and among patients with AH, CAD and DM. To confirm this conclusion well-designed large-scale studies in larger populations are needed.

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